

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some New Isomeric Pyrano[2,3-f] and [3,2-f](1,4)-Benzoxazines

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Manuscript received 26 December 1983, accepted 17 June 1984

3-Aryl-8-methyl-6-oxo-2*H*,6*H*-pyrano[2,3-f](1,4)-benzoxazine (III) 3-aryl-5-methyl-7-oxo-2*H*,7*H*-pyrano[3,2-f](1,4)-benzoxazine (IV) derivatives have been synthesised by the reductive cyclisation of *ortho*-nitro acetyl ethers, I and II over palladium-carbon. An alternate route of synthesis of the above has been achieved by the condensation of *ortho*-hydroxy amines V and VI with various *o*-bromo acetophenones to improve the yields. All these compounds have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

SEVERAL pharmacologically active compounds contain oxazine moiety¹⁻³. The condensed oxazines also possess fluorescent brightening property⁴. In continuation of our earlier work on fused heterocyclic systems^{5,6}, we describe here the synthesis and report the antibacterial and antifungal activities of the title compounds. Recent advances in the synthesis of fused oxazines have provided new routes⁷⁻¹². The synthesis of 3-alkyl-3,4-dihydro-6-oxo-2*H*,6*H*-pyrano[3,2-f]benzoxazine derivatives was reported¹³ by reductive cyclisation. As an extension, the above method was slightly modified by starting from acetyl ethers I and II by reductive cyclisation over palladium-carbon (10%) in alcoholic medium at 8 atm pressure. We could get the corresponding 3-substituted pyrano[2,3-f] and [3,2-f](1,4)-benzoxazines, III and IV, in 23% and 27% yields, respectively. Palladium-carbon has been found to be more selective to produce fused oxazines¹⁴ over Raney nickel¹⁵ which would lead to the exclusive formation of 3,4-dihydro oxazine systems.

It is an interesting point to note that at higher pressures in the range of 10-15 atm starting from compound I, a mixture was obtained. It was separated upon ptlc [Merck silica gel GF-254; ethyl acetate-hexane (75:25)+2% acetic acid]. The products isolated have been identified as 3-substituted-3,4-dihydro-8-methyl-6-oxo-2*H*,6*H*-pyrano[2,3-f]-benzoxazine along with compound III by micro analysis and spectral data.

In order to improve the yields of target compounds, the method was modified by starting with orthohydroxyamines V and VI and condensing them with various *o*-bromoacetophenones¹⁶. The yields were found to be around 50% in this route. The orthohydroxyaminopyrone derivatives V and VI have been obtained by reducing the corresponding orthonitrohydroxy compounds either on Raney nickel¹⁶ or by sodium dithionite¹⁷ in quantitative yields.

All these compounds have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data and screened against bacteria and fungi by standard methods^{18,19}.

Experimental

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Melting points were determined by open capillary method and uncorrected. The uv spectra were determined in methanol with Beckmann DK-2A spectrophotometer. IR data were obtained for KBr discs with Perkin-Elmer Model 283, ¹H nmr spectra

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-SUBSTITUTED PYRANO[2,3-f] AND [3,2-f, (1,4)-BENZOXAZINES

Compd. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.) Nitrogen	δ(CDCl ₃)
IIIa	H	223	47	4.90 (4.81)	3.1 (s, 3H) ; 4.9 (s, 2H) ; 6.3 (s, 1H) ; 7.2-8.0 (m, 7H)
IIIb	Br	210	49	3.79 (3.78)	3.1 (s, 3H) ; 5.0 (s, 2H) ; 6.3 (s, 1H) ; 7.1-7.4 (m, 2H) ; 7.7 (d, J 7Hz, 2H) ; 7.9 (d, J 7Hz, 2H)
IIIc	Cl	215	50	4.29 (4.30)	3.3 (s, 3H) ; 4.9 (s, 2H) ; 6.4 (s, 1H) ; 7.0-7.3 (m, 2H) ; 7.6 (d, J 7Hz, 2H) ; 7.8 (d, J 7Hz, 2H)
IIId	NO ₂	175	46	8.91 (8.88)	3.21 (s, 3H) ; 5.05 (s, 2H) ; 6.35 (s, 1H) ; 7.15-7.3 (m, 2H) ; 7.4-7.6 (m, 4H)
IIIe	OCH ₃	165	52	4.85 (4.86)	2.8 (s, 3H) ; 3.2 (s, 3H) ; 4.95 (s, 2H) ; 6.15 (s, 1H) ; 7.1-7.4 (m, 2H) ; 7.7-7.9 (m, 4H)
IVa	H	195	50	4.88 (4.81)	2.3 (s, 3H) ; 5.0 (s, 2H) ; 6.0 (s, 1H) ; 7.2-8.0 (m, 7H)
IVb	Br	208	53	3.79 (3.78)	2.4 (s, 3H) ; 5.1 (s, 2H) ; 6.0 (s, 1H) ; 7.2-7.4 (m, 4H) ; 7.6-7.8 (m, 2H)
IVc	Cl	218	52	4.27 (4.30)	2.3 (s, 3H) ; 5.0 (s, 2H) ; 6.0 (s, 1H) ; 7.2-7.35 (d, J 7.5Hz, 2H) ; 7.5-7.7 (m, 2H) ; 7.8-8.0 (d, J 7.5Hz, 2H)
IVd	NO ₂	220	51	8.31 (8.33)	2.6 (s, 3H) ; 5.2 (s, 2H) ; 5.9 (s, 1H) ; 7.0-7.3 (m, 4H) ; 7.5-7.7 (m, 2H)
IVe	OCH ₃	140	55	4.37 (4.36)	2.4 (s, 3H) ; 2.9 (s, 3H) ; 5.1 (s, 2H) ; 6.2 (s, 1H) ; 7.1-7.3 (m, 2H) ; 7.5-7.9 (m, 4H)

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF PYRANO[2,3-f] AND [3,2-f] (1,4)-BENZOXAZINES

Compd. no.	Concn. µg ml ⁻¹	Antibacterial				Antifungal		
		Inhibition, m.m.				Concn. µg ml ⁻¹	% Inhibition	
		<i>B. p.</i>	<i>B. m.</i>	<i>P. v.</i>	<i>P. o.</i>		<i>F. o.</i>	<i>P. v.</i>
IIIa	400	0.9	1.25	1.5	—	120	5.4	7.1
	600	1.1	1.75	2.5	—	360	12.9	15.5
						600	25.3	27.2
IIIb	400	0.5	0.9	0.75	—	840	88.6	88.6
	600	1.0	1.75	1.25	—	120	9.8	11.2
						360	12.2	19.8
IIIc	400	0.5	0.9	0.5	—	600	67.6	68.3
	600	1.3	1.6	1.0	—	840	87.4	90.5
						120	10.9	15.9
IIId	400	0.5	0.75	0.5	—	360	30.3	28.6
	600	1.0	1.25	0.7	—	600	50.5	49.5
						840	98.8	82.6
IIIe	400	3.0	3.9	1.5	—	120	10.8	17.3
	600	6.75	6.5	2.8	—	360	4.4	5.9
						600	16.9	21.0
IVa	400	0.5	0.8	0.8	—	600	42.8	45.9
	600	0.7	1.7	1.25	—	840	84.7	77.8
						120	6.7	1.6
IVb	400	0.75	1.0	1.0	—	360	16.1	17.5
	600	1.4	1.9	2.0	—	600	31.1	27.5
						840	47.5	49.3
IVc	400	0.5	0.7	0.7	—	120	1.9	5.1
	600	0.8	1.0	0.9	—	360	11.0	22.5
						600	23.2	32.8
IVd	400	0.5	0.5	0.75	—	840	46.8	48.3
	600	0.8	1.0	0.9	—	120	0.8	0.8
						360	4.4	9.1
IVe	400	0.5	0.5	0.7	—	600	10.5	23.9
	600	0.9	1.0	1.0	—	840	26.8	33.0
						120	0.9	0.9
					360	4.7	9.8	
					600	12.9	26.7	
					840	29.9	37.2	
					120	5.6	9.2	
					360	15.3	18.7	
					600	26.2	25.8	
					840	29.2	31.6	

were measured at 90 MHz on Varian A-90 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on JMS-0300 mass spectrometer at 70 eV. The physical, analytical and spectral data are given in Table 1.

3-Substituted pyrano[2,3-f] and [3,2-f](1,4)-benzoxazines: The orthohydroxyamino compounds (V or VI, 15 m mol) were dissolved in dry acetone (300 ml). The mixture was stirred rapidly at 25° for 1 h after adding anhydrous potassium carbonate (35 m mol). The ω -bromoacetophenones (12 m mol) were added to the above solution and refluxed for 6 h. The excess of acetone was distilled off, the residue washed with ice-cold water (150 ml), filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol.

Biological screening: All the compounds synthesised were screened for their antibacterial activity by Vincent and Vincent¹⁸ filter paper disc diffusion plate method. The gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria employed for the tests were *Bacillus pumilus*, *B. magaterium* and *Pseudomonas ovalis*, *Proteus vulgaris*, respectively. The results are presented in Table 2.

The antifungal activity of all the compounds synthesised was determined by the food-poisoning technique¹⁹. The fungi employed were *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Curvularia lunata*. The results are incorporated in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The general ir bands are at 1730-1700 cm^{-1} (lactonic CO) and 1610-1600 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}=\text{N}$ -stretching²⁰). The ¹H nmr spectra of both pyrano-[2,3-f] and [3,2-f]benzoxazines are similar except for a few signals; oxazine methylene [δ 5.0 (s)]; 4-methyl of coumarin system in [2,3-f]oxazines (δ 2.8-3.3), whereas the same group in [3,2-f]oxazines (δ 2.3-2.6); vinylic proton at 3rd position of coumarine (δ 5.9-6.3); aromatic protons (δ 7.0-7.3 and δ 7.5-8.0). The characteristic signals for the derivatives in the third position of oxazine unit are also being identified (Table 1).

The mass spectra of compound IIIa contains m/z (%) 291 (100), 263 (52), 262 (42), 249 (28), 160 (43), 145.5 (21), 130 (74), 103 (75) and 77 (60); compound IVa, 291 (100), 261 (27), 160 (20), 103 (70) and 77 (63).

The metastable peaks support the following transitions for compounds IIIa and IVa. m/z 291 \rightarrow 263 (M-C₆H₆ or M-CH₃N); 291 \rightarrow 262 (M-CHO); 263 \rightarrow 160 (263-C₇H₅N); 103 (C₇H₅N) and 77 (C₆H₅).

Perusal of Table 2 reveals that almost all the compounds are less toxic towards the bacteria tested. The relatively high toxicity of compound IIIe may be attributed to the *p*-methoxyphenyl

moiety. In general compounds of type III are more active than those of IV. All are ineffective towards *P. ovalis*.

The antifungal activity tests reveal that all these compounds are active against the fungi tested. The compounds IIIc and IIId are more toxic whereas compounds IVc, IVd and IVe are less. The compounds IIIa, IIIb and IIIe show maximum inhibition at 840 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Compound IIId showed 100% inhibition in both the fungi at 840 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Principal, Regional Engineering College, Warangal for providing facilities and grateful to Prof. S. R. Ramadas, I.I.T., Madras for his valuable suggestions. Two of the authors (E. S. and R. B. R.) are grateful to the U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial support and Junior Research Fellowship, respectively.

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